

Conference Abstract

Species composition of Chironomidae (Insecta: Diptera) in Vaya Lake, Bulgaria

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Abstract

During a long-term study (2003-2007) of the chironomids in Vaya Lake 27 taxa were established. There were determined 18 species belonging to 11 genera. These results were compared to the only ones so far provided by Zashev and Angelov 1958. There is a complete change in the species composition of the Chironomidae compared with the results obtained in the period 1953-1957, which is mainly related to the increased anthropogenic impact on the lake and the changed connection with the Black Sea.

Keywords

zoobenthos, anthropogenic impact

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